

MULTISCALE COMPUTATIONAL HOMOGENISATION TO PREDICT THE LONG-TERM DURABILITY OF COMPOSITE STRUCTURES

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Investigation of long-term degradation
an integrated program of computational modelling and physical testing

Involves six universities
Bath, Bristol, Glasgow, Leeds, Newcastle and Warwick

Objectives

Multi-scale analysis framework
confidence in durable composite structures

Reliability analysis for composites subject to epistemic and stochastic uncertainties

Structural-level characterisation tests
properties required for the lifetime prediction analyses

New paradigm of testing and analysis methods
To assess composites over service lives

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- ❑ Predict and describe macroscopic material behaviour by considering the mechanics of the **underlying microstructure**.

- ❑ FE², because it requires the simultaneous computation of the mechanical (thermal or moisture transport) response at two different scale.
- ❑ Advantages:
 - ❑ No explicit assumptions for the macroscopic local constitutive equations.
 - ❑ Incorporation of detailed microstructural information, including physical and geometrical evolution of the microstructures.
 - ❑ Different modelling techniques can be used on both micro-and macro-level, e.g. FEM, BEM, meshless method.

- ❑ Definition of macrostructural B.V.P.
- ❑ Definition of a microstructural representative volume element (RVE).
(with known constitutive behaviour of individual constituents)
- ❑ Formulation of the microstructural boundary conditions.
(macro-to-micro transition or localization)
- ❑ Solution of microstructural B.V.P.
- ❑ Calculation of the macrostructural output variable
(micro-to-macro transition or homogenization)

- Generalised imposition of different RVE boundary conditions (displacement, traction and periodic) [1].
- Discretised system of equations

$$\mathbf{K}\mathbf{u} + \mathbf{C}^T \boldsymbol{\lambda} = \mathbf{0}$$

$$\mathbf{C}\mathbf{u} = \mathbf{D}\bar{\boldsymbol{\epsilon}}$$

where $\mathbf{C} = \int_{\Gamma} \mathbf{H}\mathbf{N}^T \mathbf{N} d\Gamma$ and $\mathbf{D} = \int_{\Gamma} \mathbf{H}\mathbf{N}^T \mathbf{X} d\Gamma$

Homogenised stress $\bar{\boldsymbol{\sigma}} = \frac{1}{V} \mathbf{D}^T \boldsymbol{\lambda}$

- **Conduction** and **diffusion** models are considered for **thermal** and **moisture transport** problems (conservation of mass or energy for moisture and thermal problem respectively).

$$\rho C_p \frac{\partial \psi}{\partial t} - K_\psi \nabla^2 \psi = 0$$

Where

$\psi = T, c$ (scalar fields)
 ∇^2 Laplace operator
 t time
 ρ density
 C_p specific volume capacity
 K_ψ conductivity

Temperature (°C)

Moisture concentration

Model Components

Degradation model

- Experiments involves accelerated ageing with exposure temperatures of 25°C, 40°C, 60°C and 80°C and recording time of 28, 56, 112 days.

- An exponential trend is assumed for the degradation of shear modulus for all the exposure temperatures

$$G|_T = G_o e^{-\alpha t}$$

$$G|_T = \begin{cases} G_o e^{-0.0023t} & \text{for } T = 25^\circ\text{C} \\ G_o e^{-0.0027t} & \text{for } T = 60^\circ\text{C} \\ G_o e^{-0.0040t} & \text{for } T = 80^\circ\text{C} \end{cases}$$

- Generalised degradation model

$$G(T, t) = G_o e^{-\alpha(T)t}, \text{ where } \alpha(T) = \beta \ln\left(1 - \frac{T}{T_g}\right)$$

- Using least square fitting, i.e. minimising the following eq w.r.t β

$$F(\beta) = \sum_{i=1}^3 \left(\alpha_i - \beta \ln\left(1 - \frac{T_i}{T_g}\right) \right)^2$$

$$\beta = 0.001682$$

- Including effect of moisture concentration

$$G(T, c, t) = G_o e^{-\gamma(c)\alpha(T)t}$$

$$G(T, c, t) = G_o e^{-c\beta \ln\left(1 - \frac{T}{T_g}\right)t}$$

- Constant temperature and moisture concentration are assumed in the derivation of degradation model. $G(T, c, t) = G_o e^{-c\beta \ln\left(1 - \frac{T}{T_g}\right) t}$
- Assuming real scenarios of variable temperature and moisture concentration, degradation model is written in rate form as

$$G(T, c, t) = G_o e^{-c(t)\beta \ln\left(1 - \frac{T(t)}{T_g}\right) t}$$

$$\frac{d}{dt} G(T, c, t) = \frac{\partial G}{\partial T} T \cdot + \frac{\partial G}{\partial c} c \cdot + \frac{\partial G}{\partial t}$$

- Assuming chemical reaction leading to degradation of mechanical properties is very slow as compared to daily variation of temperature and moisture concentration

$$\frac{d}{dt} G(T, c, t) = \frac{\partial G}{\partial T} T \cdot + \frac{\partial G}{\partial c} c \cdot + \frac{\partial G}{\partial t}$$

$$\frac{d}{dt} G(T, c, t) = -c\beta \ln\left(1 - \frac{T}{T_g}\right) G$$

Generalised degradation model

$$\frac{d}{dt} (1 - \omega) = -c\beta \ln\left(1 - \frac{T}{T_g}\right) (1 - \omega)$$

$\omega = 0$ no degradation
 $\omega = 1$ fully degradation

- ❑ Simulation time = 1000 days
- ❑ Number of time steps = 100
- ❑ Mechanical problem was run for every 10th step
- ❑ Matrix and yarns are assumed as isotropic materials

Macro structure geometry

Macro structure mesh (561 elements, 218 nodes)

Representative volume element (10285 elements, 2364 nodes)

Mesh partition
(8 processors)

Moisture concentration

Temperature (°C)

$(1 - \omega)$ field

Vertical displacement (mm)

Moisture concentration

$(1 - \omega)$

Relative displacement (mm)

- ❑ A fully generalised mechanical degradation model has been developed for FRP composites subjected to hygro-thermal environmental conditions based on the experimental data (from our project partner).
- ❑ A coupled hygro-thermo-mechanical (considering only one-way coupling) computational framework based on multiscale (FE²) computational homogenisation, incorporating degradation model is developed and implemented in our group's FE software MoFEM.
- ❑ The developed computational framework have the flexibility of
 - ❑ Arbitrary order of approximation (hierarchic basis functions)
 - ❑ Generalized boundary conditions
 - ❑ PETSc and MOAB libraries
 - ❑ Parallel processing.

